

Identification and Prediction of Individual Response to Treatment

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Abstract

Our research delves into the treatment individualization, with a focus on predicting the individual outcome and related yet different task of assessing and predicting the effect of treatment in the individual. We address the debate around drawing causal inferences from individual cases and introduce two contrasting sets of assumptions as a foundation for two complementary analytical approaches. As a complement to the conventional population-oriented treatment effect analysis we introduce a novel approach towards analysis of the individual response to treatment. The approach combines Baconian logic with statistical analyses focusing on the interconnectedness of treatment, outcome, and covariates. It opens a possibility of drawing not uniform, limited, yet meaningful conclusions about individual response to treatment and facilitates nuanced predictions involving the individual outcomes and indicating whether the treatment is justified ineffective, or unnecessary due to anticipated spontaneous recovery. The approach aims to provide insights into personalized medical decisions, and it envisions future applications within the realms of advanced methodologies and artificial intelligence.

Key Words: treatment effect, response to treatment, potential and factual outcomes, sensitivity to treatment, spontaneous recovery, prediction

Introduction

The individualization of treatment is one of the major trends and a formidable challenge within the realm of modern medicine. Numerous studies delved into this complex issue, exploring facets such as individualization, personalized medicine, heterogeneity of treatment effect, predictive modeling, etc. However, it should be acknowledged that these investigations lack a common theoretical foundation, and their impact on clinical practice remains modest at best. Happy exceptions, such as the genetic treatment of specific cancer forms and the management of metabolic, immune, and hereditary disorders, underscore the gravity of the challenge. The crux of this issue lies in the identification and prediction of the effect of treatment in individual cases. This paper explores this problem aiming to the development of the heuristics to identify and predict the individual response to and effect of treatment.

In the ongoing dispute on the possibility or impossibility of inferences in individual cases regarding the effect of treatment, this paper supports the position that these inferences are possible within a relevant design of statistical experiment. We also demonstrate that such inferences are feasible in a purely logical context by shifting the focus from the potential outcomes framework to analysis of individual factual outcomes.

We introduce the “treatment context” as a conceptual framework for identifying determinants of individual responses to treatment via establishing correspondence between the effect of treatment and the individual’s capacity to respond. The *individual response to treatment* is considered as a complement to the traditional population-oriented analysis of the *treatment effect*. The paper formulates assumptions and proposes a model (a mix of randomly distributed and deterministically related elements) to realize this approach.

We stem from the understanding that the ways to recovery are diverse, as well as the ways to death. As a complement to studying heterogeneity of *treatment effect*, which explores the variability of outcome within the group (population) exposed to treatment, we explore heterogeneity of *individual responses to treatment* as a diversity of the factors and combinations of factors/properties/conditions related to the same outcome in individuals exposed to the same treatment.

For realization of this approach, we introduced the hierarchical framework encompassing the content-wise conceptual (“treatment context”), formal (interpreted in terms of sets), and operational (binary data matrix) levels.

We employ specified forms of logical reasoning and introduce them as tangible analytical instruments to generate data-driven hypotheses about the interconnections between treatment, conditions, and outcomes. Logical analysis is complemented with statistical analysis of these interconnections.

We suggest the receptor-marker framework, which provides a unified way to understand how rare and prevalent variables interact across different levels of analysis. It leads to the identification and not uniform, yet comprehensive, and clinically significant predictions of the *individual response to treatment*.

This investigation resulted in the heuristics for identifying the individual response to treatment within the trial population (RCT in our case) and predicting (with inevitable limitations, of course) the individual response to treatment beyond the boundaries of the RCT population.

1 Major controversy

There is a consensus that randomized controlled trials (RCT) provides a uniform, quantitative scientific approach towards the assessment of the efficacy of treatment. This undisputed advantage makes the RCT approach a gold standard for the assessment of the effect of drugs, and one of the cornerstones of the system of drug development. Naturally, this approach has blind spots, controversies, and limitations extensively discussed in literature, but does not have yet a satisfactory solution, e.g., as follows.

Unlike results of statistical experiments in agriculture, physics, mechanics, etc., the individual effect of treatment is of the existential concern for each individual patientⁱ but translating a result of RCT to an individual patient, as well as generalizing the result to the “real world” populations is always problematic.

There is a notion shared by many statisticians that making causal inferences from an individual case even is not possible.^{ii,iii} Some of them declare that “identifying individual causal effect ... even does not make sense.”^{iv}

Conversely, the examples of inferences derived from analysis of single cases can be found in classic statistics.^v There are approaches employing a single case design and utilizing statistical apparatus for drawing inferences.^{vi} There is a branch of applied statistics aiming to identify and predict *individual treatment effect* considering it as a function of covariates. Exemplary studies of this branch offer significant methodological insights and leveraging advanced statistical methodologies effectively.^{vii} Yet the interpretation of the results as the identification and prediction of the *individual treatment effect* raises substantial concerns.

This paper aims to demonstrate that the *individual effect of treatment*, although appears intuitively clear, cannot be identified in the frame of the commonly accepted statistical definitions. Its identification and prediction require more complex logical determinations, especially when the predictions extend beyond the boundaries of the trial (RCT) population.

2 Previous steps

This paper is a continuation of our report^{viii}, in which we approach this controversy as follows. When an unprejudiced investigator observes two co-occurring events and is trying to learn whether there is an association between them, one of the first things should be forming a hypothesis of whether these events have co-occurred by chance or were related to each other directly, meaning temporal, spatial, structure, content-wise, symbolic, or causal relationships. Initially, both assumptions are equally legitimate, leading the further analysis in different directions. Ultimately the results of the two analysis paths are compared, and the initial hypothesis of each analysis should be accepted or rejected.

2.1 Complementary approaches.

From this unprejudiced position, we have proposed complementing the approach towards analysis of the *treatment effect* with the approach towards analysis of the *response to treatment*. The *treatment effect* is a population concept defined in RCT and observational studies as risk reduction for a negative outcome. We have defined the *response to treatment* as the individual reaction to the applied treatment, realized as one or another of the alternative potential outcomes.

2.2 Assumptions.

The *treatment effect* and *response-to-treatment* approaches derive from different assumptions designating the opposite starting positions of analysis.

The *treatment effect* (RCT) approach implicitly assumes that

1. Subjects are anonymous and interchangeable.
2. Two or more events co-occur by chance unless the contrary is proven
3. Numerous subjects are required for making valid inferences

For *response to treatment*, we assume that

1. Each subject is a unique individual
2. Two or more co-occurring events are related unless the contrary is proven
3. Valid inferences potentially can be made from single cases

These are not positive assertions, but rather the assumptions in a genuine meaning of this term, designating starting positions of two complementary approaches.

2.2.1 Population models

We employed two models in parallel: (1) the RCT population commonly modeled as a set of a randomly distributed elements and (2) the same RCT population modeled as a mix of the randomly distributed elements and deterministically related components composed from the same elements (“soup”).^{ix} The elements (variables) of our population model are not related across individuals, and they can be or not be deterministically related within the individual. The model is described in detail in^x.

2.3 RCT dataset

The models (1) and (2) are realized using the RCT binary dataset as a frame.

Figure 1. Heterogeneity of response to treatment in the trial population

On Fig.1, the population is described respectively in two complementary ways, presenting two different images (A, B).^{x1} In this space, a single case is a vector of the variables including treatment, outcome, and covariates. On Fig.1(A), before sorting, a configuration of the elements of the matrix is visibly chaotic. On Fig.1(B) the same data have been sorted to demonstrate the object of our interest, which is the group of color-coded assemblages of variables including treatment, outcome and subset of covariates.

2.4 Definitions and notation

We reuse a notation, set of definitions, and the RCT binary data matrix as a technical framework for analysis of the treatment process from our previous reports.

Operating under the assumption that *Two or more co-occurring events are related unless the contrary is proven*, we regard the events having co-occurred as related rather than solely attributing their co-occurrence to *randomness* (per the Oxford dictionary). Alternatively, following the understanding commonly accepted in mathematics, computer science, and physics, we consider events to be related *deterministically* when “no randomness is involved.” Henceforth, “deterministic” is used exclusively in this sense.

We use the term “causal” for the factors/events deterministically related to the outcome of interest, and which are included in the set/chain of the factors/events “recognized as responsible for the production of a given outcome.”^{xii}

In some of the cited texts, the term “causal” is used by their authors in a more broad, general sense. This difference should be clear from the context.

3 Objectives

1. Introduce the factual (observed) outcomes framework as a complement to the potential outcomes framework for analyzing individual response to treatment.
2. Define and describe the "treatment context" as a set of interconnected concepts, events, and relationships centered around the curative connotation of treatment.
3. Explore the possibilities and limitations of drawing meaningful conclusions about individual response to treatment within the treatment context.
4. Develop a conceptual, formal, and operational framework for combining logical and statistical analysis of individual treatment cases in various contexts, including a. Pairwise comparisons; b. Samples; c. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) datasets; d. Observational datasets
5. Employ logical instruments for data-driven hypothesis development in the context of treatment response analysis.
6. Investigate the potential for predicting individual response to treatment beyond training and test sets, extending to the general population.
7. Delineate the possibilities and limitations of such predictions for individual treatment response.
8. Develop heuristics for predicting individual response to treatment.

4 “The Lady tasting tea”

As mentioned above, a common notion among statisticians is that drawing valid inferences regarding the effect of treatment in a single case is impossible. We are inclined to support the opposite notion illustrating it with a chrestomathy example.

Generations of statisticians learned the principles of statistical experiment from the case the Lady tasting tea, which provides a comprehensive description and explanation of the blind randomized design, the method of analysis of results, the concept of the “null hypothesis,” and the approach toward proving significance of the results.^{xiii}

As stated by the author, Ronald Fisher, the experiment was designed “to test the assertion” by the Lady “...that by tasting a cup of tea made with milk she can discriminate whether the milk or the tea infusion was first added to the cup.”

In many respects, the design of this experiment similar the blind randomized controlled trial (RCT) with one substantial and commonly unnoticed difference. Like RCT, the experiment compares two treatments in a series of randomized installments, in which the sequence of the infusion of milk and tea, as well as the sequence of the installments was not known to the subject. Unlike RCT, in the Lady tasting tea experiment, the trial population included only one, single, subject, the Lady.

4.1 Dual goal of experiment

Note that the primary goal of the experiment was to confirm or refute the capacity of the Lady to discriminate the differently prepared samples. The only way to do it was to identify and therefore to prove that the samples prepared using two different ways have a discernable difference in taste.

If the capacity of the Lady to discriminate the samples, i.e., her sensitivity, was not that sharp, or if the difference in the taste between the samples was below the threshold of her sensitivity, the Lady would find herself in an uncomfortable position of having made the assertions that could not be confirmed (fortunately, history says that the Lady has correctly identified all 8 experimental samples). Also, the World would not have

the benefit of knowing - with all signs of scientific persuasiveness - that the sequence of the infusion of tea and milk into the cup – does change the taste of this mixture.

In the process of the experiment, two facts have been established: 1) the change in the way of preparing tea changed its taste to the extent that 2) the single subject of the experiment was capable of having identified and has identified this difference.

Therefore, experiment has a dual nature. Drawing valid inferences from the individual case became possible upon establishing *correspondence* between the sufficient *effect* of the different treatments on the taste of tea - and capacity of the Lady to discern the difference in the taste of the samples, i.e., her the *sensitivity* to this effect.

4.2 Generalization issue

A specific result of the concrete experiment – a capacity to discern the portions of tea prepared using two different methods - refers only, exclusively, to the Lady, personally Ms. Blanche Muriel Bristol, who was the subject of this experiment. It cannot be extrapolated to the general population, or to the population of ladies, or even narrowly to the group of those who were present at the terrasse where Ronald Fisher performed his experiment. To learn whether one of these generalizations could be true, we should design other experiments involving representative samples of subjects, under a defined set of conditions, and involving different statistical methodology. Without it, we cannot state - with all signs of scientific persuasiveness – that other Ladies, or people of both genders - also may have this capacity. It would be pure speculation.

On the other hand, this limitation, i.e., a lack of generalizability, is the major characteristic of this design, its distinctive feature designating the in-principle possibility of making a valid logical and statistical inference in a single case.

Strictly speaking, the results of the experiment refer only to the quantities, proportions, sort of tea and sort of milk, etc. conditions under which this experiment has been performed. Generalizing this effect and widening the boundaries for this generalization require special assumptions, which - to tell the truth - are very rarely formulated explicitly.

4.3 In summary:

- In the context of the adequately designed statistical experiment, the inferences from single cases are possible.
- One of the possible designs considered above involves one subject exposed to multiple episodes of treatment such that each episode is a random installation of one of two (or more) standard treatments.
- Experiment explores a *correspondence* between the capacity of the treatment to impose its effect onto the subject - and the capacity of the subject, under the circumstances, to react to this treatment with producing a particular outcome. While having identified the effect of treatment, we congruently establish the fact of the capacity of the subject to respond to it, and *vice versa*: establishing one implies the existence of another.
- The inference from a single case refers to this case only. It should not be generalized beyond the subject, as well as beyond the scope of the modalities of the treatment involved in the experiment.

5 Potential outcomes framework

Originally, *The Lady tasting tea* case was used to illustrate the principles of the statistical experiment, but regardless of the intentions, it has provided a theoretical background and a prototype of the statistical single case design, i.e., it has confirmed that causal inferences from a single case are possible.

Paradoxically, the population approach towards the assessment of the *treatment effect*, which emerged in the form of the randomized controlled trial (RCT), has derived from the assumption of inability of making causal inferences from a single case, which is a logical foundation of the potential outcomes framework introduced by Jerzy Neyman.^{xiv} The potential outcomes framework stemmed from the note that every experimental unit exposed to treatment had two (in a binary system) different potential outcomes.

Let a person exposed to treatment Tx have the outcome Y . In the theory of the potential outcomes, it is assumed that if the patient had been exposed to treatment tx , he/she could potentially have either outcome y or Y (in a binary system), which can be written as

$$Tx(Y); tx(y, Y).$$

To measure the effect of Tx over tx , the investigator should look at two outcomes in the same individual: the outcome Y , which has been observed in the patient who has been treated with Tx , and one of the potential outcomes (y , or Y) if he/she was treated with tx . The difference between these outcomes is thought to be an indication of the effect, but it is not known which of the potential outcomes would have occurred, i.e., one of the outcomes needed for comparison is always missing. "The unhappy conclusion is that, in general, individual causal effects cannot be identified because of missing data."^{xv}

This conclusion is designated as the "fundamental problem of causal inference."^{xvi} A solution for this fundamental problem was seen in comparing not individuals, but rather the groups of the observed outcomes in the individuals assigned to different treatments. If the assignment to treatments Tx and tx is random, the groups are (on average) equivalent, and the difference in outcome is the only difference between the groups. Therefore, it can be attributed to the treatment assignment. The difference between the groups is typically used as a measure of the *treatment effect*.

5.1 Two paths

This logic motivated the development of the Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) approach, focusing on the population-level treatment effect. The next logical step was the integration of covariates into the potential outcomes framework, which enabled remarkable theoretical advancements. It made possible studying heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE), which developed into a fast-progressing area.^{xvii} The propensity scoring approach data has emerged, which enabled analyzing the treatment effect using observational data.^{xviii} Moreover, the concept of potential outcomes and counterfactual thinking constitute fundamental aspects of statistical causality theory.^{xix}

Collectively, these developments provide a robust foundation for analyzing the population-level treatment effect. However, when addressing individual treatment effects, challenges arise due to the inherent absence of one potential outcome, making it logically impossible to assess the treatment's effect on an individual. This reality regarding potential outcomes is undeniable.

Paradoxically, there is an opportunity, largely overlooked by the investigators, of making logically valid inferences concerning the individual effect of treatment via considering instead the individual factual (observed) outcomes. Below we will demonstrate that although these causal inferences may not be as standardized as those in statistical treatments of the treatment effect, they can significantly contribute to

identifying and predicting the individual response to treatment and, consequently, the individual treatment effect.

5.2 Definition of individual treatment effect

Defining the individual treatment effect is a challenging task. Emphasizing this difficulty, Donald Rubin, whose name is related among other achievements to a further development of the potential outcomes framework, provides the following definition: “Intuitively, the causal effect of one treatment, E , over another, C , for a particular unit and an interval of time from t_1 to t_2 is the difference between what would have happened at time t_2 if the unit had been exposed to E initiated at t_1 and what would have happened at t_2 if the unit had been exposed to C initiated at t_1 : 'If an hour ago I had taken two aspirins instead of just a glass of water, my headache would now be gone,' or 'because an hour ago I took two aspirins instead of just a glass of water, my headache is now gone.' Our definition of the causal effect of the E versus C treatment will reflect this intuitive meaning.”^{xx}

While statistically accepted, this intuitive definition raises questions from a position of a physician. Asserting that aspirin would have relieved the headache is not necessarily true: potentially, either positive or negative outcomes were possible. Moreover, the positive outcome (“headache is gone”) could have occurred due to aspirin or regardless. Clinical experience reveals positive outcomes upon taking aspirin and without it. The statement 'If an hour ago I had taken two aspirins instead of just a glass of water, my headache would now be gone' is rooted in intuition rather than certainty. Ascertaining aspirin's effect would require evidence that the positive outcome occurred because of aspirin and not otherwise, which as we know from the analysis of the potential outcomes framework is not feasible.

While the potential outcomes regarding taking “two aspirins” remain uncertain, we can confidently make a strong evidence-based statement about another treatment under discussion: “a glass of water” was not effective in this patient. It is factual and indisputable. Below, we delve further into this line of reasoning.

5.3 Ramifications

The ambiguity in defining the individual treatment effect complicates understanding and explaining counterfactual causality,^{xxi} especially in clinical scenarios. Indeed, it is difficult to accept without resistance the counterfactual statement, for instance, about the patient who died after heart transplantation, such as “If Zeus did not have surgery, he would survive.”^{xxii} For a clinician, at the very least, thorough explanations of the circumstances under which this statement could be true are required.

The concept of the potential outcomes implies more than one outcome. Without surgery, Zeus's chance of survival was negligible, which made necessary the potentially lifesaving, yet risky, complex, traumatizing, and expensive transplantation. Evaluating the operation's risks and benefits should be the aim of counterfactual analysis. Yes, the surgery was not effective for Zeus, but there is no ground for the statement “If Zeus did not have surgery, he would survive,” which sounds like a verdict against heart transplantation. Apparently, using the operator “probably” (likely, possibly, apparently, evidently, etc.) would make this statement more accurate both in mathematical and clinical sense.

We deem this clarification necessary because our analysis below is specifically focused on the agreement between the statistical, logical, and clinical concepts under consideration, as well as on the distinction between the probabilistic statements and the positive statements made with certainty, as a matter of fact.

5.4 Diversity of experiments

Treatment is an experiment in a broad sense of this term. The experiments differ by numerous characteristics, and treatment has both common and distinctive features compared to other types of experiment, important for analysis. The typology of experiments should be a matter of separate studies. For our purposes, we will compare the treatment with a few selected types of experiment differing by their design and the possibility of predicting a result.

We consider a variety of the types of experiment as a continuum along the axis of predictability of the result and mark this axis with the following examples.

A lottery, where the result of the experiment is completely by chance, is thought to be at one pole of this continuum. The opposite pole of the continuum could be marked by the stamping of identical items with a press, where the purpose of the process, components, and conditions are structured in such a way that the outcome of each action (experiment) is identical and predictable. Between these extremes, there is a variety of types of experiment. We point out distinctive features of some types of experiment allegedly located at the different points of the lottery-stamping axis.

5.5 Types of experiment

Consider the counterfactual statements referring to the experiments named above: a lottery, freeway or highway (as presented by Judea Pearl^{xxiii}), treatment, and stamping.

“If I did not turn the press on, there would not be a product”

“If I purchased a lottery ticket from another kiosk, I would possibly win a jackpot”

“If I used a highway, instead of the freeway, I would probably reach my destination earlier”

“If I have taken aspirin instead of glass of water, my headache would probably have now gone.”

All four statements have an identical logical structure. All four directly or indirectly report about an observed outcome; both set to answer the same question "what would have happened if" and provide “a probabilistic answer to this question.”^{xxiv}

5.5.1 Stamping

The counterfactual result of stamping is entirely predictable: as far as the experiment has occurred, the outcome is positive. Otherwise, no action - no product. Formally, it also can be described in probabilistic terms as the probability of a negative counterfactual outcome 100%.

5.5.2 Lottery

The participant of the well-designed lottery has a miniscule chance to win, and beyond that the individual result cannot be predicted. It does not depend on any circumstance (e.g., geographical area, age of a gambler, purchasing the ticket from one or another kiosk, a date, time of the day, exerting some actions or rituals etc., etc.), i.e., the lottery is designed to make the individual outcome of the participation completely by chance. In this sense, the design of the lottery and design of stamping are symmetrical.

The outcomes, both factual and counterfactual, of the events described in other statements (freeway vs. highway, and treatment) could be different depending on the conditions, on the context, in which the events took place.

5.5.3 Freeway vs. highway

Generally, the scenario of the choice between a freeway or highway, as presented by Judea Pearl,^{xxv} is a model to a variety of situations of choice and decision making. It encompasses a range of very distinctive situations, e.g., the choice between the highway and freeway, going to Harvard vs. local community college, having or not having heart transplant surgery, etc. Yet the theory, abstracting from the concrete content and meaning of the events, actions, and relationships, describes the very distinctive “physical” situations in probabilistic (statistical) terms. It employs a “population thinking” and sophisticated statistical analysis, and instructs to create structure equations, to develop predictive models, decision trees, etc.

5.5.4 Treatment

The term "treatment" encompasses various meanings depending on its context of use. It may denote an independent variable or a component within an experimental setting, or it may carry its original connotation of curative intervention. Hereafter, we consider the term “treatment” in its genuine curative connotation (unless other indicated), which creates a range of specific possibilities for analysis.

5.5.5 Case Z_1

Let us describe the cited case “If Zeus did not have surgery, he would survive” in a symbolic form: Z can exist in one of two states: Y or y . The event Tx may occur (Tx) or not occur (tx). Given the observed events y and Tx formally represented as (Tx, y) , the determination of Tx 's effectiveness is not feasible without having defined relationships between the symbols.

5.5.6 Case Z_2

The patient Z suffers from a disorder leading to the potential outcomes such as recovery (Y) or death (y). The decision to undergo heart transplantation (Tx) or not (tx) is pivotal. In the specific instance where Z undergoes surgery (Tx) but subsequently dies (y), the treatment Tx for Z is ascertainably ineffective (regardless of having been effective in other cases). This assertion is possible due to the contextual specificity afforded by employing the term "treatment" in its curative context.

6 Treatment context

While using the term “treatment” in its curative connotation, we enter a specific meaningful context, a universe, where the formal statement, for instance, $In_j \supset Tx, y$, which refers to the individual In_j treated with Tx and having a negative outcome, is embedded to an unlimited network of contents and concepts, to a complex of the events, states, relationships, sequences, structures, and meanings. These instances are numerous and diverse, but at the same time, this concept of treatment involves multiple invariants closely related to each other.

Particularly, in a curative connotation, the term “treatment” is implicitly bound content-wise to the term “patient” or “subject,” and therefore, the expression $In_j \supset Tx, y$; implicitly means that

- the patient is a member of the population, specifically, the population of patients suffering from the disorder of interest;

- the patient is meant to be involved into the process, in which he/she had some baseline state;
- at some unidentified moment of time, this patient was exposed to the action of some hypothetically curative agent;
- exposure to the *treatment* is – implicitly or explicitly – preceded with a hypothesis that it is supposed to inflict (or prevent) some changes in the state of the subject;
- implicitly, in a binary system, the expression $In_j \supset Tx, y$; has a quantitative aspect: e.g., one (1) patient treated with 1 instance of treatment has 0 outcomes Y ;
- the exposure endured some unidentified period of time;
- *treatment* is a transformative action; it is to inflict the desirable (or prevent not desirable) change in the subject, i.e.,
- it implicitly includes the *do* operator;
- before the treatment has been performed, there were (in a binary system) two potential outcomes, positive (i.e., expected, desirable) or negative, only one of which will be observed;
- in the process of the treatment, by the end of the defined period, the baseline state either changed or did not change which resulted in the form of the observable outcome;
- a positive outcome can be a result of the treatment, or it can occur regardless of it;
- treatment can be or not be effective;
- treatment was effective if and only if the positive outcome has been induced by the treatment; otherwise, the positive outcome was spontaneous, i.e., it cannot be attributed to the effect of the treatment;
- the treatment can be effective only if the (patient) subject is sensitive to this treatment, i.e., these concepts are symmetrical and corresponding;

This list can be continued *ad infinitum*.

Thus, the term *treatment*, if it is used in its genuine curative sense, creates a context, (skeleton, structure, frame) implicitly including all features of experiment, and composed of the objects, events, and relationships providing a framework for both logical and statistical inferences involving analysis of individual both potential and factual (observed) cases. Hereafter, this framework will be termed the “treatment context.”

6.1 Inferences within treatment context

Formally, within the framework of potential outcomes theory, isolating the effect of treatment in an individual case presents a challenge due to the inherent uncertainty surrounding what the outcome would have been in the absence of treatment. However, as we shown above, the assertion that “individual causal effects cannot be identified because of missing data”^{xxvi} holds true specifically within the realm of potential outcomes. Contrastingly, when considering factual (observed) outcomes, a basis exists for making valid inferences.

The estimation of the *treatment effect* typically involves comparing groups of factual outcomes through randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and observational study designs. As previously established, within a statistical context and with specialized designs, valid inferences can indeed be drawn at the individual level. Here, we aim to demonstrate that within the treatment context, valid causal inferences can be made even through purely logical reasoning, even when information is restricted to observed outcomes and treatment status.

In such instances, identifying the effectiveness of treatment within observed outcomes becomes akin to discerning a missing piece of a puzzle. Addressing this logical and psychological puzzle enables the formulation of limited yet valid and meaningful inferences regarding the individual treatment effect.

Subsequently, we navigate through a system of logical relationships where missing information on certain variables can be inferred from contextual cues.

6.2 Treatment effect: Logical Perspective

Within a binary system, there are four types of the combinations of treatment and outcome, termed as “treatment-outcome complex”: Tx, y ; $tx \cap Y$; $Tx \cap Y$; and $tx \cap y$.^{xxvii}

Consider four individuals (In_j):

$$In_1 \supset Tx \cap y;$$

$$In_2 \supset tx \cap Y;$$

$$In_3 \supset Tx \cap Y;$$

$$In_4 \supset tx \cap y.$$

Examining the case limited to $In_1 \supset Tx \cap y$, formally, no inferences can be drawn beyond acknowledging that Tx and y are associated with In_1 . However, within the treatment context, it is unequivocally deducible that in an individual subjected to treatment Tx having resulted in a negative outcome y , the treatment was ineffective. This deduction is pertaining solely to In_1 . It does not necessitate counterfactual analysis.

Similarly, in the case of $In_2 \supset tx \cap Y$, where the patient was not exposed to treatment yet experienced a positive outcome, it is evident that recovery Y was not caused by treatment Tx . This inference, devoid of counterfactual comparison, is unequivocal.

Subsequently, in the case of $In_3 \supset Tx \cap Y$, where treatment Tx was administered and a positive outcome occurred, it remains possible that recovery (Y) was indeed induced by treatment Tx . However, certainty cannot be asserted as recovery Y could have manifested irrespective of treatment Tx .

Lastly, $In_4 \supset tx \cap y$ represents an instance where no basis for inferences regarding the effect of treatment Tx is available. This formalization aligns with D. Rubin's example where the subject, opting for a glass of water instead of aspirin, continues to suffer from a headache.

Hence, within the framework of the "treatment context," valid causal inferences can be drawn for the factual (observed) individual cases, even when information is restricted to a combination of treatment and outcome, termed as the "treatment-outcome complex." While these inferences lack uniformity, they hold meaningful significance. The level of certainty varies depending on the observed combination of treatment and outcome.

Definitive inferences can be made with certainty in cases of $Tx \cap y$ and $tx \cap Y$. In $Tx \cap Y$ cases, the positive outcome can be either spontaneous or it can be attributed to the effect of the effect of Tx . Neither of these possibilities can be conclusively ruled out.

The combination $tx \cap y$ provides no insight into the effect of treatment Tx .

It's noteworthy that these inferences concerning treatment effects are derived within a logical, not statistical, context. They do not necessitate the analysis of counterfactuals. Rather, they involve logical deductions within the treatment context, akin to finding missing puzzle pieces or identifying and inserting absent components to restore the integrity of the "treatment context."

6.3 Determinants of response to treatment

Analysis of the classic example above reveals that the treatment's effectiveness *corresponds* to the subject's properties. At a physical level, these attributes can be diverse and manifold, stemming from both internal and

external factors. Our report ^{xxviii}extensively discusses this complexity. From a logical standpoint, these factors can be generalized and classified as *sensitivity to treatment* (St) and/or the capacity for spontaneous recovery (Sp), i.e., the properties of the individual determining his/her response to treatment. Hereafter, for brevity, the term “properties” will be used for St and Sp . A positive outcome is contingent upon the individual being either sensitive (St_+) to the treatment or possessing the capacity Sp_+ for spontaneous recovery. Conversely, a negative outcome arises when these properties are absent (St_-, Sp_-). Note that the properties (St_+, Sp_+) are not mutually exclusive.

Typically, St or/and Sp are missing in the description of the individual. However, having observed the outcome in the patient exposed to the treatment, we can deduce that this factual outcome may have occurred if and only if the patient had the relevant properties. Thus, upon observing the outcome of the defined treatment in an individual, we can deduce, although with different level of certainty, the presence or absence of either or both properties: (Sp_+, St_+), (Sp_+, St_-), (Sp_-, St_+), (Sp_-, St_-).

6.4 Why has the patient had recovered?

In the binary system, the “treatment-outcome complex” presents four modalities: $Tx \cap y$; $tx \cap Y$; $Tx \cap Y$; and $tx \cap y$.^{xxix} Each individual having one of these combinations also has a set of covariates (conditions). Given that the diverse conditions can be categorized into two non-mutually exclusive properties (St and Sp), we can infer the following.

The patient $I_1 \supset Tx \cap y$ has not exhibited the outcome Y in response to treatment Tx , which indicates a lack of *sensitivity* to the treatment the treatment, as well as *no capacity for spontaneous recovery*, i.e., $I_1 \supset Tx \cap y; \rightarrow St_-; Sp_-$.

Conversely, the individual $I_2 \supset tx \cap Y$; certainly, demonstrated the *ability to recover spontaneously*. It is unclear whether this individual was also *sensitive* to the treatment Tx . It can be expressed as $I_2 \supset tx \cap Y; \rightarrow Sp_+, St_{\approx}$; where St_{\approx} denotes a possibility of presence of the property St_+ .

Individual $I_3 \supset Tx \cap Y$; could be *sensitive* to the treatment Tx , capable of *spontaneous* recovery, or have possessed both properties, which is expressed as $I_3 \supset Tx \cap Y; \rightarrow St_+ \cup Sp_+; St_+ \cap Sp_+$. The only impossibility is possessing neither ($St_- \cap Sp_-$).

Regarding the case of $I_n \supset tx \cap y$, while it lacks information about the effect of treatment Tx , it is deducible that the individual did not have the capacity for spontaneous recovery (Sp_-). Additionally, while it cannot be confirmed, it also cannot be ruled out that treatment with Tx if applied to this patient, might yield a positive outcome. Thus, the individual definitively does not possess the *capacity for spontaneous recovery*. The *sensitivity to treatment* Tx can be neither confirmed nor denied: $I_4 \supset tx \cap y; \rightarrow Sp_-, St_{\approx}$.

6.5 Summary

Within the “treatment context,” valid causal inferences can be drawn for factual (observed) individual cases, even when information is restricted to a combination of treatment and outcome, termed as the “treatment-outcome complex.” The foundation of the inferences is the *correspondence* between the capacity of the treatment to induce the changes leading to the observed outcome, and the capacity of the subject to produce the outcome in response to the treatment (for brevity, the “effect-response” system). While these inferences lack uniformity, they hold meaningful significance. Alternatively, the individual can develop the positive outcome due to his/her capacity to recover spontaneously. The content, comprehensiveness, and the level of certainty varies depending on the observed combination of treatment and outcome, but for each of the possible “treatment-outcome complexes” the inferences can be drawn with certainty regarding the one or another substantial aspect of the system “effect-response.”

It is certain that

- individual In_1 in the case $In_1 \supset Tx \cap y$; does not have the property Sp_+ , i.e., a capacity to recover spontaneously; individual In_2 in the case $In_2 \supset tx \cap Y$; has the property Sp_+ , and has recovered spontaneously;
- individual In_3 in the case $In_3 \supset Tx \cap Y$; cannot be lacking both Sp_+ and St_+ ;
- individual In_4 in the case $In_4 \supset tx \cap y$; does not possess the property Sp_+ .

Besides, additionally, the inferences can be drawn with a lesser level of certainty, yet clinically important, for each of the cases.

It's noteworthy that these inferences concerning treatment effects are derived within a logical, not statistical, context. They do not necessitate the analysis of counterfactuals. Rather, they involve logical deductions, akin to finding missing puzzle pieces or identifying and inserting absent components to restore the integrity of the "treatment context."

These inferences operate at the category level, i.e., the determinants of the response to treatment manifest as categories, i.e., they are lacking a "physical" image that would allow to designate their identity and recognize them via comparing with other members of the group, population. It should be done through filling these categories with clinical content. It requires considering these categories from a clinical perspective.

7 Clinical considerations: two aspects of heterogeneity

7.1 Heterogeneity of Treatment Effect

As previously mentioned, assessing the *treatment effect* necessitates statistical comparison of the *observed* outcomes in the populations exposed and unexposed to the treatment. Clinical investigations and studies on heterogeneity of treatment effect highlight the influence of both internal and external factors on outcomes.

Besides, clinical observations show that *various individuals exposed to the same treatment can exhibit the same or different outcomes*. At the population level, this phenomenon is studied as Heterogeneity of Treatment Effect (HTE), which manifests as substantial variations of risk in clinically significant subgroups exposed to the same treatment, compared to the Average Treatment Effect (ATE). Generally, the deviations are considered as a function of covariates. A nowadays methodological level and major achievements of this rapidly developing approach are shown by Kent et al. (2020).^{xxx}

This aspect of heterogeneity faces challenge in identifying and predicting the individual treatment effect, as well as in going beyond the boundaries of the clinical trial, i.e., the results of studying HTE on the population of a clinical trial cannot be translated to the general population.

7.2 Heterogeneity of RCT population

Clinical observations also show that individuals with the same outcome can have been exposed to the same or different treatments. Even further, the individuals exhibiting the same outcome and exposed to the same treatment can be related to various factors. Some of these factors are similar in the members of this subgroup, while others are different.

It points to another, less studied aspect of heterogeneity, specifically, different ways of reaching the same outcome, or in other words, the different ways to respond to treatment.

Consider a typical RCT design schematically shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Diagram of Placebo-Controlled Randomized Trial

The experimental group, in which all patients were exposed to the same treatment, falls to two ultimately distinctive groups - with positive and negative outcomes. The same is true about the control (placebo), i.e., both groups are heterogenous. Also, a proportion of positive and negative outcomes in these groups is different. This is the first level of heterogeneity in the considered aspect.

7.3 Heterogeneity of positive outcomes

Then, since the placebo is biologically inactive, the patients with a positive outcome in the control cohort have recovered with no treatment, i.e., spontaneously (for simplicity, we do not consider the “placebo effect”^{xxxix}). Thus, in the placebo control, there is a fraction of spontaneously recovered patients. If the trial was randomized 1:1, it should be expected that in the experimental cohort, there should be an amount of spontaneously recovered patients (Spontaneous) approximately equal to that in the placebo control.

Therefore, in the experimental cohort, the recovery can be positively attributed to the experimental treatment only in the rest of patients with positive outcome (Treatment-induced). These relationships are inherent to the randomized placebo-controlled design, but they are not included in the concept and practice of the assessment of the treatment effect by apparent reasons: The Spontaneous and Treatment-induced cases are not clinically distinguishable, although the ways of the development of the positive outcome (recovery) were different. There are reasons to believe that both Spontaneous and Treatment-induced subgroups also can be heterogenous, and below, we consider the approach towards the identification and differentiation of these subgroups, sub-subgroups, and individuals.

7.4 Heterogeneity of negative outcomes

A separate, yet similar issue is the heterogeneity of the group of patients with negative outcomes. While some patients could have died from the target disorder, the others could have died from other causes. Once again, the outcome itself, death, is not distinguishable in these patients, and to establish the differences in the causes of death is the prerogative of the clinical, pathology, etc. analyses.

Altogether, in terms of causality, the RCT data present a complex mosaic (Fig. 3) not sufficiently accounted for in the analysis of the treatment effect.

Figure 2. Diagram of Randomized Placebo-Controlled Trial

As mentioned above, it is impossible to tell based on clinical observation, in which member of the experimental cohort a positive outcome, recovery, should be attributed to the effect of treatment, and in which it has developed spontaneously, regardless of the treatment. Also, some of the negative outcomes (deaths) were not caused by the target disorder. Rather the negative outcome (death) was caused by the disorder of interest, or by diverse lethal factors (infections, accidents, intoxications, etc.). In clinical trials, these cases are usually grouped as All Cause Deaths.

Also, death can have occurred from the disorder of interest in cases, in which it would not have occurred if the patient was not exposed to additional morbid factors (malnutrition, heart, kidney, hepatic insufficiency, concurrent disorders, etc.). In turn, these factors can be present or absent in individual patients in various combinations, and some can be grouped in various patient samples.

7.5 Heterogeneity of response to treatment

Typically, in RCT these diverse individual causes of death are identified by clinical and pathology analysis, i.e., causal relationships between death and certain factor or a combination of factors have been established independently for each individual, with maximum possible accuracy, irrespective of frequency of these factors in the trial population. It means that at least in some cases the causal relationships between some clinically observable factors and the outcome can be positively identified.

The causes of death confirmed with clinical and pathology analysis in each individual case treated with the same treatment can be diverse. It indicates that the individual ways of reaching the same outcome in response to the treatment can be diverse.

In this sense, the cause of death in each individual case may be different, and the causal factors or combination of factors can be similar in some and different or unique in other individuals.

In summary, the ways to recovery are diverse as are the ways to death. Complementary to heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE), which explores the variability of the outcome within the group of patients exposed to the treatment, heterogeneity of the individual response to treatment is understood as a diversity of the factors and combinations of factors/properties/conditions related to the same outcome in individuals exposed to the same treatment

8 Factual outcomes framework

The potential outcomes framework, which in the binary system can be written as $(Tx; Y)(tx; y, Y)$ derives from a logical analysis of the treatment effect in an individual case concluding that causal inference is impossible because one of the potential outcomes cannot be observed. Consequently, it resorts to statistical comparisons of outcomes between groups assigned to different treatments, where the outcome is a function of treatment and conditions.

Clinical observations on more than one individual (clinical, epidemiological, or experimental datasets) containing information on the applied treatments and factual (observed) outcomes reveal that:

1. Various individuals exposed to the same treatment can exhibit the same or different outcomes.
2. Individuals exposed to different treatments can likewise exhibit the same or different outcomes.

As far as information is restricted to observed outcomes and treatments, these observations can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} Tx, Y; \\ Tx, y; \\ tx, Y; \\ tx, y. \end{aligned}$$

Upon introducing covariates potentially influencing the outcome, the factual outcomes framework can be formulated generally as $(Tx, tx)(Y, y)$, or more detailed as:

$$\{\mathcal{S}\} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A \supset S_A, Tx, Y; \\ B \supset S_B, Tx, Y; \\ \dots \dots \dots \\ C \supset S_C, Tx, y; \\ D \supset S_D, Tx, y; \\ \dots \dots \dots \\ E \supset S_E, tx, Y; \\ F \supset S_F, tx, Y; \\ \dots \dots \dots \\ G \supset S_G, tx, y; \\ G \supset S_H, tx, y; \\ \dots \dots \dots \end{array} \right\};$$

where $\{\mathcal{S}\}$ – the set of internal and external factors uniformly describing the patient population. In a clinical context, $A, \dots, B, \dots, C, \dots$ denote individual patients described with the subsets of covariates S_A, S_B, S_C, \dots

Like the Neyman-Rubin framework, the presented factual outcomes framework operates with concepts of treatment, outcomes, and covariates, but these components are treated as the sets of observed events. This framework facilitates comparisons between subsets of patients, treatments, and covariates, enabling both logical and statistical operations. Notably, it allows for standalone analysis of observed outcomes, independent of potential outcomes contexts, thus enabling the examination of responses to treatment in individuals and small groups.

Technically, the binary data matrix presented earlier serves as a practical realization of the factual outcomes framework for such analyses. Just a reminder that analysis of the *treatment effect*, stemming from the concept of the potential outcomes is practically realized (RCT) as comparing the groups of factual (observed) outcomes.

9 Mapping properties: Principles of analysis

9.1 Modeling individual treatment response

As indicated earlier at the clinical level, as well as at the logical level, the *response to treatment* may be influenced by one or multiple factors, either internal or external, which could be similar or different across individuals. In individuals exposed to treatment, the outcome is contingent upon their inherent properties (St and/or Sp) that determine their response. Our subsequent focus lies in examining the avenues to identify and delineate these properties, which are manifested through covariates. Essentially, our goal is to pinpoint the covariates that are associated with sensitivity to treatment (St) and capacity for spontaneous recovery (Sp).

As a reminder, we approach the relationships between variables within the framework of two distinct models. One model, which is commonly used in studies on *treatment effect* treats the elements of the matrix as randomly distributed. However, for studying *individual responses to treatment*, we proposed an alternative model, blending randomly distributed and deterministically related elements.

Under our model and assumptions, it's anticipated that certain covariates in individual may exhibit deterministic relationships, forming clusters. The clusters may be similar across some individuals and different across others. We term the set formed by the subset of individuals with identical clusters of deterministically related variables as an *aggregation*. Some of the aggregations can include both treatment and outcome. As shown above, as far as we have observed the treatment and outcome in the patient, we can infer his/her corresponding properties (*St* or/and *Sp*).

Our subsequent task involves exploring the ways for identifying (mapping) the covariates that are deterministically related to the properties *St* and/or *Sp* within the set of covariates describing the individual. Additionally, randomly distributed variables may also give rise to visually similar groupings within the data matrix (the case-variable associations). Distinguishing between these aggregations and case-variable associations poses a significant challenge in studying heterogeneity and predicting treatment responses.

Here, we delve into two primary dimensions of mapping analysis: logical and quantitative. As the number of factors and individuals involved continues to grow, the complexity of this analysis inevitably escalates. Our aim in this section is to outline the fundamental principles of this analysis, serving as conceptual guidance for computerized mapping, potentially leveraging technologies such as neural networks, machine learning, deep learning, and AI.

9.2 Logical analysis

Analysis is aimed to identify the variables potentially (*possibly*) related to the properties forming the *response to treatment*. The approach is stemming from logic of Francis Bacon^{xxxii} who believed that the cause of the phenomenon should be deduced by elimination of the factors not matching the occurrence of the phenomenon. Inductive reasoning should be applied to the factors co-occurring with the phenomenon.

For example, "...if an army is successful when commanded by Essex, and not successful when not commanded by Essex: and when it is more or less successful according to the degree of involvement of Essex as its commander, then it is scientifically reasonable to say that being commanded by Essex is causally related to the army's success."^{xxxiii}

Importantly, Francis Bacon emphasized that this inference is not conclusive. This is only a hypothesis, which must be scrutinized and compared to other hypotheses. In fact, this approach does not positively identify the causal factor, i.e., factor "responsible for the production of a given outcome in a specific scenario." Rather it eliminates the factors which are not involved in potentially causal relationships.

The inferences within this logic can be true within a limited context. Within a broader context the same logic also can be applied and can be true to other names, segments of time, scope of people involved, events, and circumstances. In the example above, the virtual variable designating a series of military successes of the Elizabethan era is marked with many glorious victories, glorious names, as well as some challenging episodes, i.e., it is heterogenous.

The major obstacle to the realization of Francis Bacon's approach would be the hard to overcome difficulty in delimiting each period and delineating the context of each episode. Besides, following this logic we eliminate the factors that cannot be considered as related to the Earl Essex's success; among the remaining, not eliminated factors, one can find some, which are related deterministically (in the narrow sense defined

above), but not necessarily causally. Also, deterministically related factors can exist among those eliminated, presenting as indicators, markers, accessories, etc., of Essex’s success.

Despite these limitations, we employ this approach for the development of the hypotheses (subject to further scrutiny) about the *individual response to treatment* and anticipating that it will lead to the hypotheses about the heterogeneity of this effect. Having utilized this logic, we eliminate the factors (covariates) for which causal relatedness should not be attributed to the property(ies) determining the effect of treatment, and therefore, we expect having identified the factors potentially causally related to the property Sp_+ (capacity for spontaneous recovery) and/or property St_+ (sensitivity to the treatment). For these explorations, we will use the samples of the records from the RCT dataset.

9.2.1 Sample

In Table 1, there is a mock sample from the RCT dataset. The population is described with a set of binary variables $Tx, Y, A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I$. The sample may not be randomly selected. Let this one be selected and is chosen to encompass individuals with all possible combinations of treatment and outcome (Tx, Y ; Tx, y ; tx, Y ; and tx, y).

$(Tx \cap Y)$	$A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I$
$In_1 \supset (tx \cap Y)$	$A, B, C, d, E, f, G, h, I$
$In_2 \supset (tx \cap y)$	$A, b, C, d, e, F, G, h, i$
$In_3 \supset (T \cap Y)$	$A, B, C, d, E, f, G, h, i$
$In_4 \supset (Tx \cap y)$	$A, b, C, d, e, F, g, h, i$
$In_5 \supset (tx \cap Y)$	$A, B, c, D, e, F, G, h, I$
$In_6 \supset (tx \cap y)$	$A, b, c, D, e, f, G, H, i$
$In_7 \supset (Tx \cap Y)$	$A, b, c, D, e, f, G, h, i$
$In_8 \supset (Tx \cap y)$	$A, B, c, D, e, f, g, h, i$

Table 1. Sample of individuals treated with Tx

where In_j represents the individual (case); A, B, \dots, I – denote variables, where each variable can take the values 0 or 1, i.e., $A = a, A = 0,1$; $B = b, B = 0,1$; A combination of the variables Tx, Y is treated as a single variable ("treatment- outcome complex"). The color codes are explained within the text.

9.2.2 Case 1. Single case

Consider an individual $In_1 \supset (tx \cap Y); A, B, C, d, E, f, G, h, I$; as a standing alone case, i.e., out of the context of the sample X. As shown above, the “treatment-outcome complex” $tx \cap Y$ indicates that the individual In_1 is in possession of the property Sp_+ , i.e., he/she was capable of (and in fact had) spontaneous recovery.

The possibility of logical analysis (mapping) in this single case is limited. because there is no information about other members of the sample. This set of variables cannot be compared with other ones. It means that any of the covariates describing this individual cannot not be eliminated until additional information indicates the opposite. At this point, any of the variables describing In_1 may be considered as potentially related to Sp_+ , although it cannot be neither confirmed, nor rejected.

9.2.3 Pairwise comparisons (typology and principles)

Additional possibilities for exploring the relationships between the properties determining *response to treatment* and covariates (St or/and Sp) emerge if other individuals come to observation. A major instrument for analysis is comparing the individual with other individuals, samples, and populations, and using Bacon’s logic, the variables that cannot be related to the properties St or/and Sp are eliminated.

Four types of the “treatment-outcome complex” allow for 10 types of the pairs:

$$\begin{aligned}
 In_1In_2 &= (tx \cap Y), (S_1) - (tx \cap y), (S_2); \\
 In_1In_3 &= (tx \cap y), (S_1) - (Tx \cap Y), (S_3); \\
 In_1In_4 &= (tx \cap Y), (S_1) - (Tx \cap y), (S_4); \\
 In_1In_5 &= (tx \cap Y), (S_1) - (tx \cap Y), (S_5); \\
 In_2In_3 &= (tx \cap y), (S_2) - (Tx \cap Y), (S_3); \\
 In_2In_4 &= (tx \cap y), (S_2) - (Tx \cap y), (S_4); \\
 In_2In_6 &= (tx \cap y), (S_2) - (tx \cap y), (S_6); \\
 In_3In_4 &= (Tx \cap Y), (S_3) - (Tx \cap y), (S_4); \\
 In_3In_7 &= (Tx \cap Y), (S_3) - (Tx \cap Y), (S_7); \\
 In_4In_8 &= (Tx \cap y), (S_4) - (Tx \cap y), (S_8);
 \end{aligned}$$

where (S_i) is a subset of co-variates. Each of the types of the pairs has unique respective logic of inferences regarding the mapping.

The comparison of the individuals comprising the pair is the core of analysis at the initial stage of the mapping. The pairwise comparisons are the prototype of logical analysis of more numerous samples and an integral part of the consecutive comprehensive stages of the exploration.

Analysis of some pairs can lead to certain positive or negative conclusions. Other analyses allow for a limited number of variants, and, lastly, a conclusion in some cases can be uncertain. A positive result of the pairwise comparison is not the assertion that, e.g., the variable A is related to the property Sp_+ . Rather it is the statement that such a possibility is not ruled out, which makes it a step in the complex process of the causality assessment. The result of the comparison refers separately to each of the individuals comprising the pair.

Case 2

Let us map the property S_+ in the individuals of the pair In_1 and In_2 .

$$\begin{aligned}
 In_1 &\supset (tx \cap Y), A, \mathbf{B}, C, d, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{f}, G, h, \mathbf{I}; \\
 In_2 &\supset (tx \cap y), A, b, C, d, e, F, G, h, i.
 \end{aligned}$$

Apparently In_1 has the property Sp_+ and In_2 does not. All variables describing In_2 cannot be related to the property Sp_+ . Some of the covariates describing In_1 are identical to the covariates of the (A, C, d, G, h) of In_2 and cannot be related to the property Sp_+ too. Therefore, only the covariates $\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{I}$ can possibly be causally related to the property Sp_+ in the individual In_1 .

An important reservation is that these inferences are true in the frame of analysis of this pair. In other pairs, different hypotheses can be made regarding each of these variables. Also, the factors related to the property Sp_+ also could reside among the “not included” as well as among “not known” covariates.

Case 3

In the pair,

$$\begin{aligned}
 In_3 &\supset (Tx \cap Y), A, \mathbf{B}, C, d, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{G}, h, i; \\
 In_4 &\supset (Tx \cap y), A, b, C, d, e, F, g, h, i;
 \end{aligned}$$

the member In_3 can have the property Sp_+ as well as St_+ or both. The member In_4 can be in possession of neither Sp_+ , nor St_+ . Therefore, neither of these properties describing In_4 can be considered being related deterministically to the variables A, C, d, e, F, G, h , and i . Thus, this comparison suggests that the property Sp_+ , in which we are currently interested, possibly can be related to the variables $\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{f}$, or \mathbf{G} , which are present in the individual In_3 . In some instances it is similar to the previous comparison, and in the other ones it is not.

Case 4

In the pair

$$\begin{aligned} In_2 &\supset (tx \cap y), A, b, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{d}, e, \mathbf{F}, G, \mathbf{h}, i; \\ In_6 &\supset (tx \cap y), A, b, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{D}, e, \mathbf{f}, G, \mathbf{H}, i; \end{aligned}$$

both members do not possess the property Sp_+ . Certainly, the covariates describing both In_2 and In_6 , i.e., $A, b, C, c, D, d, e, F, f, G, H, h, i$ should be eliminated from considering as being potentially related to the property Sp_+ . Yet for the covariates a, B, D, E, g , which are not present in the description of the pair In_2 and In_6 , this possibility is not ruled out, and this information should be reserved for other analyses.

Case 5

Consider the pair In_1 and In_5 .

$$\begin{aligned} In_1 &\supset (\mathbf{tx} \cap \mathbf{Y}), \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, C, d, E, f, \mathbf{G}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{I}; \\ In_5 &\supset (\mathbf{tx} \cap \mathbf{Y}), \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, c, D, e, F, \mathbf{G}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{I}; \end{aligned}$$

Each of the pair members has the combination $\mathbf{tx} \cap \mathbf{Y}$, i.e., each of them has the property Sp_+ . Following the logic of the examples above, it can be concluded that the property Sp_+ can *possibly* be related to the covariables $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{G}, \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{I}$ in both In_1 and In_5 .

Case 6

In the pair (In_3, In_7) , each of the members can have the property Sp_+ as well as St_+ or both.

$$\begin{aligned} In_3 &\supset (Tx \cap Y), A, B, C, d, E, f, G, h, i; \\ In_7 &\supset (Tx \cap Y), A, b, c, D, e, f, G, h, i; \end{aligned}$$

The only inference can be made with certainty is that it is impossible for both In_3 and In_7 to have neither Sp_+ nor St_+ . Beyond this, analysis reveals multiple variants neither of which can be logically preferred. Meaningful preferences can be inferred upon coming beyond the boundaries of the pair and comparing the members of this pair with other members of the sample (e.g., Case 3), which is a separate logical problem.

9.2.4 Mapping in sample

Case 7

At the initial step, analysis of the sample $In_{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8}$ can be approached the same way as the pairwise comparisons, i.e., via elimination of the variables that cannot be potentially causally related to the property Sp_+ (or St_+).

In the individuals In_2, In_4, In_6 , and In_8 , the entire sets of the covariates can be eliminated because these individuals do not possess the property Sp_+ . Also, the variables $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{F}, \mathbf{G}, \mathbf{H}$ should not be considered at this point in all members of the sample since each of them is observed both in the individuals having and not having the property Sp_+ . Therefore, only the variable \mathbf{I} (highlighted purple) in the individuals In_1 and In_5 can be potentially causally related to the property Sp_+ . This is a possibility, not necessity.

In fact, this is the first order analysis of the sample. It will be shown below that the hypotheses generated at this step can be complemented (not overwritten) by more detailed, e.g., pairwise comparison, analysis. The latter cannot be overwritten by the analysis of the sample as well.

Thus, valid data-driven hypotheses can be drawn from a limited number of observations, particularly in the contexts such as the treatment of rare disorders, family genetics, pharmacogenetics, and exploratory stages of clinical research, where the population-oriented studies require extensive time and resources.

9.3 Increasing sample

In the statistical context, we could try to isolate or consolidate some of the hypotheses via increasing the sample, e.g., as $In_{1,\dots,16}$. This is not a possibility in the logical context.

	$(Tx \cap Y)$	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
In_1	$\supset (tx \cap Y)$	A	B	C	d	E	f	G	h	I
In_2	$\supset (tx \cap y)$	A	b	C	d	e	F	G	h	i
In_3	$\supset (Tx \cap Y)$	A	B	C	d	E	f	G	h	i
In_4	$\supset (Tx \cap y)$	A	b	C	d	e	F	g	h	i
In_5	$\supset (tx \cap Y)$	A	B	c	D	e	F	G	h	I
In_6	$\supset (tx \cap y)$	A	b	c	D	e	f	G	H	i
In_7	$\supset (Tx \cap Y)$	A	B	c	D	e	F	G	h	I
In_8	$\supset (Tx \cap y)$	A	B	c	D	e	f	g	h	i
In_9	$\supset (tx \cap Y)$	A	B	c	D	e	F	G	h	I
In_{10}	$\supset (tx \cap y)$	A	b	c	D	e	f	G	h	i
In_{11}	$\supset (Tx \cap Y)$	A	B	C	d	E	f	G	h	i
In_{12}	$\supset (Tx \cap y)$	A	b	C	D	e	f	G	H	i
In_{13}	$\supset (tx \cap Y)$	A	B	c	d	e	F	g	h	i
In_{14}	$\supset (tx \cap y)$	A	b	c	D	e	f	G	H	i
In_{15}	$\supset (Tx \cap Y)$	A	b	C	d	e	F	G	h	I
In_{16}	$\supset (Tx \cap y)$	A	B	c	d	E	f	G	h	i

Table 2. Sample of individuals treated with Tx

Considering the enlarged sample (Table 2), we can also hypothesize that the property Sp_+ (and, therefore, a positive outcome) can be possibly related to the variable F . Importantly, that we do not have any reason to question the hypotheses previously generated based on analysis of the pairs, sample and sub-samples. i.e., instead of consolidating any of the hypotheses shown above, the increase in the sample has only increased the diversity of the hypotheses. Logically, they all are equally viable. Each of them refers to the relevant sub-sample, i.e. validity of each of them is a matter of additional quantitative, structure-functional, content-wise analysis. At this point, the presented diversity illustrates a hypothetical structure of the heterogeneity of response to treatment in the above indicated sense.

Particularly, based on the available information, it can be hypothesized that in the sample $In_{1,\dots,16}$ there are several variants of possible association of the property Sp_+ with covariates. Particularly, in some individuals (and/or groups of individuals) the property Sp_+ , can be linked to the variable I , in others - to the variable F , and in the others – to different variables and/or clusters of the variables. Simplifying, the same outcome in various individual can be related to various factors and combinations of factors.

The examples above are focused on mapping the property Sp_+ . Similar logic should be used for mapping Sp_+ . Readers are encouraged to extend this analysis, leveraging the demonstrated logic to the types of pairs and samples not illustrated above.

9.4 Heterogeneity of response to treatment in logical context

Examination of clinical databases often reveals a notable dissonance between the perceived clinical relevance of certain study factors and their attenuated or marginal significance within a statistical framework. Intuitively, one of the most plausible explanations for such discrepancies lies in the heterogeneity of the factors involved. This intuition finds support in clinical observations and the growing body of evidence amassed through the framework of Heterogeneity of Treatment Effect (HTE) analysis.

As formulated above, we understand heterogeneity of *response to treatment* as a diversity of the factors and combinations of factors determining response to the treatment among various individuals exposed to the same treatment. Also, it refers to small and large groups, members of which are exposed to the same treatment and united by common factors/properties determining the type of the response. This understanding of heterogeneity of *response to treatment* was presented above at the clinical level. Here, we discuss the way of exploring this heterogeneity using a logical apparatus.

9.5 Back to pairwise comparisons

Analysis of pairwise comparisons reveals similarities and differences between the pair members. As to comparing the pairs to each other,

$$\begin{aligned} In_{1,2}(* B * * E f * * I); \\ In_{3,4}(* B * * E f G * *); \\ In_{2,6}(a B * D E * g * *); \\ In_{1,5}(A * * * * * G h I); \end{aligned}$$

the “selected” covariates and clusters of the covariates (i.e., those potentially related to Sp_+) can be identical in some of the pairs and different in the others.

Similarly, the “eliminated” covariates during pairwise comparisons are identical across certain pairs but vary in others.

$$\begin{aligned} In_{1,2}(A * C d * * G h *); \\ In_{3,4}(A * C d e F G h *); \\ In_{2,6}(A b * * e * G, * i); \\ In_{1,5}(* * C d E f * * *); \end{aligned}$$

The pair $In_{3,7}$, is standing alone because logically any covariates of the individuals In_3 and In_7 could be potentially related to the property Sp_+ . Note also that in the considered sample $In_{1,\dots,8}$, covariates A , G , and h are present both among “selected” and “eliminated” covariates.

Within the statistical population model, this distribution of the covariates can have a formal explanation as evidence of randomness.

One of the complementary initial positions of our investigation is the deterministic one. The behavior of the deterministically related elements within the population (sample) should adhere to stricter rules. Particularly, having observed the binary covariate A , G , or h both among the “selected” and “eliminated” requires more comprehensive explanations. In this case, these variables could not maintain consistent meaning and values across the sample.

Firstly, such discrepancies could be attributed to data entry errors or vague definitions of the variables. Assuming these factors have been adequately addressed in our sample, the most plausible explanation should be that within the sample, covariates like A , G , and H are differently associated with the property Sp_+ . While phenomenologically they may appear homogeneous overall, certain elements or segments might diverge in their relationships with other variables. This observation aligns with clinical observations above. It does not prove, but rather provides the data driven hypotheses that the same outcome can be determined in various individuals and groups of individuals by different factors and combinations of factors.

9.6 In summary

The logical mapping analysis is to generate data driven hypotheses concerning the potential relationships between covariates or clusters of covariates and specific properties denoted as Sp_+ and St_+ within an

individual. In various individuals, the property Sp_+ as well as St_+ can be linked to various variables or clusters of the variables. On the other hand, certain variables, (e.g., $A, G,$ or h) can be linked to the property of interest (e.g., Sp_+) in some individuals and not be linked to this property in other individuals of the sample. It means that the properties Sp_+ (or St_+) and the cluster of logically related to this property variables can be hypothetically considered either as a hierarchical structure with the properties Sp_+ and/or St_+ at the top of the hierarchy, or as non-hierarchical aggregations of the factors determining the response to treatment.

This image of heterogeneity aligns with the factual outcomes framework, as well as with the clinical observations above indicating that the same outcome can be determined in various individuals and groups of individuals by different factors, clusters, and categories of factors.

The combination of treatment, outcome and covariates observed in an individual case can be explained by various logically valid hypotheses depending on the context in which the individual was observed. The hypothesis generated on an individual or a small sample cannot be extrapolated to another sample. Also, the hypothesis generated from a small sample cannot be overwritten by the hypothesis deriving from the larger one and *vice versa*. They should coexist in individuals, in small or large groups, and in the frame of hierarchical structures, unless proven invalid.

Therefore, the logical analysis provides a data-driven hypothesis encompassing a set of logically possible variants of the heterogenous structure of the population (group, subgroup, sample), which is are subject to temporal, structure-functional, content-wise, and quantitative analysis. The latter is discussed in the next section.

9.7 Quantitative aspect

9.7.1 Co-occurrence of rare events in a defined statistical context. Aggregation

In **Cases 1 - 6** above, the individuals have been non-randomly selected from the RCT dataset. The RCT population described with a set of binary variables $Tx, Y, A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I$. The parameters of the variables are thought to be known. Some of the variables have been designated above as rare ones, i.e., the statistical context for considering the cases is strictly defined.

Let us consider the individual In_1 (**Case 1**) described by a set of binary variables:

$$In_1 \supset \{tx \cap Y, A, B, C, d, E, f, G, h, I\}$$

Hereafter, for convenience of presentation, we discuss the individuals with the variable $(tx \cap Y)$ which indicates a possession of the property Sp_+ . Analysis of other combinations of treatment and outcome $[(Tx \cap Y), (Tx \cap y), (tx \cap y)]$, which refer in various ways to either property Sp_+ , or St_+ , or both, follows the same principles, although it requires adjustments because of the content differences.

The probability of each variable occurring in individual I_l can be estimated based on its frequency in the trial population: $Pr_{In_1}(tx \cap Y); Pr_{In_1}(A), Pr_{In_1}(B), \dots, Pr_{In_1}(h), Pr_{In_1}(I)$.

Just a reminder that we do not assess the association or a lack of association between variables, e.g., A and B . Rather, our focus lies in determining whether the events A and B in a single individual In_1 have occurred together by chance or because they are linked deterministically.

To assess whether two rare events A and B co-occur by chance in individual I_1 , we calculate:

$$Pr_{In_1}(A \cap B) = Pr_{In_1}(A) \cdot Pr_{In_1}(B).$$

If this probability falls below a predetermined criterion Cr , we accept the hypothesis that A and B are deterministically related in I_1 .

For multiple rare events, e.g., A, B, C, E, G, I this analysis can be extended as:

$$\begin{aligned} & Pr_{In_1}(A \cap B \cap C \cap E \cap G \cap I) = \\ & = Pr_{In_1}(A) \cdot Pr_{In_1}(B) \cdot Pr_{In_1}(C) \cdot Pr_{In_1}(E) \cdot Pr_{In_1}(G) \cdot Pr_{In_1}(I). \end{aligned}$$

Let Cr be a predetermined criterion. If $Pr_{In_1} < Cr$, we consider these events as forming an *aggregation*. In this context, we introduce the receptor-marker concept:

1. The individual In_1 can be viewed as having a "receptor" for the rare events A, B, C, E, G, I .
2. Conversely, the co-occurrence of these rare events serves as a "marker" for a specific characteristic of In_1 .

This correspondence between the individual's characteristics (receptor) and the rare event cluster (marker) forms the basis for identifying deterministic relationships.

An alternative approach using Bayes' theorem:

$$Pr_{In_j}(A|B) = \frac{Pr_{In_j}(B|A) \cdot Pr_{In_j}(A)}{Pr_{In_j}(B)}.$$

In summary, unlike the *treatment effect*, which is established via assessing the difference between the groups of treated and untreated patients conditioned on the set of covariates, in analysis of the *response to treatment* we explore two aspects of the relatedness between treatment, outcome and covariates in an individual:

1. Based on logical analysis, we hypothesize the causal relationships between treatment, outcome, and selected covariates.
2. Using quantitative analysis, we aim to establish the deterministic relationships between treatment, outcome, and covariates via their interconnectedness as assessed by the probability of their chance co-occurrence in a specific individual.

The causal and deterministic aspects of the relationships should be complemented and validated with the spatial, temporal, structure-functional, and content-wise analysis.

9.8 Co-occurrence of rare and prevalent variables

9.8.1 Within statistical paradigm

Another way of exploring a potential *aggregation* can start with the identification of the cluster of variables identical in two or more individuals. The cluster may include rare and/or prevalent variables.

Consider the pair of individuals $In_{1,5}$.

$$\begin{aligned} In_1 & \supset (tx \cap Y), A, B, C, d, E, f, G, h, I; \\ In_5 & \supset (tx \cap Y), A, B, c, D, e, F, G, h, I. \end{aligned}$$

Both individuals comprising the pair $In_{1,5}$ have an identical cluster of variables including rare covariates A, B, G, I as well as the prevalent variables $(tx \cap Y)$ and h .

The events $(tx \cap Y), A, B, G, h, I$ could have co-occurred either by chance or not by chance. Like the above,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Pr_{In_1}[(tx \cap Y) \cap A \cap B \cap G \cap h \cap I] = \\ & = \Pr_{In_1}(tx \cap Y) \cdot \Pr_{In_1}(A) \cdot \Pr_{In_1}(A) \cdot \Pr_{In_1}(B) \cdot \Pr_{In_1}(G) \cdot \Pr_{In_1}(h) \cdot \Pr_{In_1}(I). \end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\Pr_{In_1}[(tx \cap Y) \cap A \cap B \cap G \cap h \cap I] = \Pr_{In_5}[(tx \cap Y) \cap A \cap B \cap G \cap h \cap I];$$

and the probability of the chance co-occurrence of the events A, B, G, h, I and $(tx \cap Y)$ in both In_1 and In_5 is as small as

$$\Pr_{In_1 \cap In_5}[(tx \cap Y) \cap A \cap B \cap G \cap h \cap I] = \Pr_{In_1}[(tx \cap Y) \cap A \cap B \cap G \cap h \cap I]^2.$$

Thus, like the co-occurrence of rare events above, the inference regarding a deterministic vs. random character of the linkage between the variables $(tx \cap Y) \cap A \cap B \cap G \cap h \cap I$ hinges on the interconnectedness of treatment, outcome, and covariates, gauged by the probability of their chance occurrence. The co-occurrence of rare and prevalent variables extends the receptor-marker concept:

1. The prevalent variable $(tx \cap Y)$ may contain a segment that acts as a "receptor" for the rare event cluster A, B, G, I
2. The rare event cluster A, B, G, I serves as a "marker" for this specific segment of $(tx \cap Y)$.

This approach differs from analysis of co-occurring rare variables only by the way of selecting the covariates and individuals, but since the variable $(tx \cap Y)$ is prevalent, the effectiveness of the criterion Cr used above can be problematic.

9.8.2 Within deterministic paradigm

Apparently, the rare variables of the cluster A, B, G, I in individuals I_1 and I_2 form an aggregation $Ag_{In_{1,5}}^{A,B,G,I}$. The variable $(tx \cap Y)$ is prevalent, and as shown above its relationships with the aggregation $Ag_{In_{1,5}}^{A,B,G,I}$ are yet to be established.

We can hypothesize that H: $Ag_{In_{1,5}}^{(tx \cap Y), A, B, G, I}$, which suggests that:

1. A segment $(tx \cap Y)'$ of the prevalent variable $(tx \cap Y)$ acts as a "receptor" for the rare event cluster (A, B, G, I) .
2. The rare event cluster A, B, G, I serves as a "marker" for the presence of $(tx \cap Y)'$.

The probability of chance co-occurrence of $(tx \cap Y)$ and A, B, G, I in the individuals In_1 and In_5 can be calculated as

$$\Pr(Ag_{In_{1,5}}^{(tx \cap Y), A, B, G, I}) = \Pr[(tx \cap Y) | In_{1,5}] \cdot \Pr(A, B, G, I);$$

where $\Pr((tx \cap Y) | In_{1,5})$ follows binomial distribution

$$\Pr((tx \cap Y) | In_{1,5}) = \Pr(k) = \binom{N}{k} \cdot p^k \cdot (1-p)^{N-k};$$

and k is the number of individuals comprising the segment $In_{1,5}$ of the entire RCT population N ; $P(k)$ is the probability of having exactly k individuals of N ; p – the probability of k estimated in the context of the entire population as $\frac{k}{N}$.

If the probability $\Pr((tx \cap Y), (tx \cap Y)')_{In_{1,5}}$ falls below the criterion Cr we can conclude that:

- 1) $Ag_{In_{1,5}}^{(tx \cap Y), A, B, G, I}$ constitutes the aggregation, and
- 2) The variable $(tx \cap Y)$ is heterogenous as far as it contains segments $(tx \cap Y)$ and its complement.
- 3) In turn, the variable $(tx \cap Y)$ also is heterogenous as far as it contains segments $(tx \cap Y)'$ and its complement.
- 4) The segment $(tx \cap Y)'$ acts as a "receptor" for the rare event cluster A, B, G, I .
- 5) The rare event cluster A, B, G, I serves as a "marker" for the presence of $(tx \cap Y)'$.

In other words, the variable $(tx \cap Y)$ is a hierarchical structure involving the heterogenous factors determining response to treatment.

9.9 Co-occurrence of prevalent variables

Let $A = A, a$; $B = B, b$; $C = C, c$; represent potentially heterogenous variables. Within our population model, which assumes a mixture of deterministically related and randomly distributed elements, we extend the receptor-marker concept to prevalent variables. If a segment a' of the prevalent variable a and a segment c' of the prevalent variable c are deterministically related to the rare variable B , then a', B, c' are related deterministically, i.e., a', B, c' constitute an aggregation. In this context:

1. a' and c' act as "receptors" for the rare event B .
2. B serves as a "marker" for the presence of a' and c' .
3. a' and c' also serve as "markers" for each other, mediated by their common relationship with B .

This extended receptor-marker relationship helps identify hidden structures within and between prevalent variables that may influence treatment response.

9.9.1 Application to Treatment Response

Consider the prevalent variables $(tx \cap Y)$ (treatment and outcome) and h (another prevalent characteristic). We hypothesize:

1. A segment $(tx \cap Y)'$ of $(tx \cap Y)$ is deterministically related to a cluster of rare variables A, B, G, I .
2. A segment h' of h is also deterministically related to the same cluster A, B, G, I . Under these conditions, we can form an aggregation: $Ag_{In_{1,5}}^{(tx \cap Y)', A, B, G, h', I}$

This aggregation suggests that:

1. $(tx \cap Y)'$ and h' act as "receptors" for the rare event cluster A, B, G, I .
2. The cluster A, B, G, I serves as a "marker" for the presence of $(tx \cap Y)'$ and h' .

3. $(tx \cap Y)'$ and h' serve as "markers" for each other, mediated by their common relationship with A, B, G, I .

9.9.2 Implications for Treatment Response Analysis

The considerations above refer to the variable $(tx \cap Y)$ which indicates that the individual carrier of this variable possesses the property Sp_+ . With adjustments required due to the content differences, this approach is also applied to analysis of the property St_+ , and it allows us to:

1. Identify hidden structures within prevalent variables that may influence treatment response.
2. Recognize subgroups of individuals who share similar deterministic relationships between variables.
3. Potentially predict treatment response based on the presence of specific rare event clusters (markers) or prevalent variable segments (receptors).

9.10 Summary

This refined approach traces the progression of the receptor-marker concept from rare event co-occurrences to relationships between prevalent variables. It assesses the hypothetical hierarchical heterogeneous structure of factors determining response to treatment at individual and subgroup levels, focusing on the interrelatedness of variables within a population model characterized as a mixture of deterministically and randomly associated elements.

The receptor-marker framework provides a unified way to understand how rare and prevalent variables interact across different levels of analysis, potentially leading to more nuanced and personalized treatment strategies.

10 Predicting individual response to treatment

The currently most recognized approach towards predicting the results of treatment is conceptualized as Predictive Heterogeneity of Treatment Effects (HTE) analysis. A comprehensive account of Predictive HTE analysis presented by Kent et al. (2020) encompasses central ideas, trends, challenges, advances, and limitations of this approach. The Predictive HTE approach signifies an expansion of the analytical instrumentation, enhancing the accuracy of treatment effect predictions. At the core of this approach lies the concept of the population level *treatment effect*, rooted in the potential outcomes framework, and defined as risk reduction for negative outcomes. The studies referred to in this paper employ a broadly defined regression methodology for analyzing the population of a randomized clinical trial. Heterogeneity of treatment effect is construed as the nonrandom variation in the magnitude or direction of a treatment effect across levels of a covariate. The declared aim of predictive HTE analysis is to furnish patient-centered estimates of outcome risks with and without intervention, accounting for all relevant patient attributes simultaneously. Some of the advanced studies employing this approach claim identifying and predicting the *individual treatment effect*. The studies representing this approach demonstrate evident progress in the methodology and important theoretical findings. Naturally, this approach also has limitations discussed below.

10.1 Individual outcome vs. individual effect of treatment

In the realm of predictive HTE analysis, the work by the international group of statisticians aiming to identify individual treatment effect^{xxxiv} warrants particular attention. From a statistical standpoint, it stands as a sophisticated exemplar, offering significant methodological insights and leveraging advanced statistical

methodologies effectively. The study demonstrates high accuracy in identifying and predicting outcomes for individual RCT subjects, both exposed and unexposed to experimental treatments.

The authors of this study recognize that the high accuracy of their predictions was achieved within the trial population and cannot be extrapolated to the general population. This limitation inherent to the studies adopting a population-oriented *treatment effect* approach is also known as the “efficacy-effectiveness gap.”

Secondly, the cited study did not identify and predict the *individual treatment effect*. Within the RCT population, it has identified and predicted with high accuracy the individual outcome (which is important), but it was not the *individual treatment effect*. These are two distinct concepts.

The outcome is a state, i.e., condition, status, a resulting (or initial) state of the illness and/or treatment process. The *treatment effect* is the characterization of the process of treatment having resulted in this outcome. The very concept of potential outcomes implies that in the individual exposed to treatment one of two outcomes (in the binary system, positive or negative) should have occurred. The *individual effect of treatment* should mean that the outcome in this individual has (or has not) occurred *because* of the treatment, or at least the treatment was a part of the chain or assembly of the factors/events “recognized as responsible for the production of a given outcome in a specific scenario.”^{xxxv}

10.2 Efficacy-effectiveness gap

In clinical research, epidemiology, in the predictive HTE analysis,^{xxxvi} the assessment and prediction of the effect of treatment operates with the concept of risk, which is understood as a probability of a negative outcome estimated as a proportion of this outcome in the studied population; this definition implicitly refers to a population, not individual.

A widespread view among statisticians is that the assessment of the effect of treatment in an individual case is impossible specifically because the identification of individual risk is not possible.^{xxxvii} “The ubiquitous presence of individual-level variability makes it impossible to study individual-level causal effects.”^{xxxviii}

The “efficacy-effectiveness gap” emerges from the difficulty of translating statistical estimates of the *treatment effect* from RCT (efficacy) to the general population (effectiveness).^{xxxix} Accordingly, the accuracy of predicting individual outcomes within an RCT population does not necessarily extend to individual members of the general population.^{xl} Summarizing the experience of numerous clinical studies, McEvoy, et al., (2014) conclude that (1) predictions of risk are accurate at the level of populations but do not translate directly to patients, and (2) perfect accuracy of individual risk estimation is unobtainable even with the addition of multiple novel risk factors.^{xli}

In our opinion, the leading statistical factor of the “efficacy-effectiveness gap” is the non-random, based on the specific inclusion/exclusion criteria, selection (recruiting) of the RCT subjects from the general population.

To illustrate, consider a general population (G) as a data matrix with randomly distributed binary variables, including treatment, outcome, and covariates. The trial dataset (Tr) is a non-random sample of G . Training sample (Tr_A) and test sample (Tr_B) are the random subsets of Tr , sharing nearly identical parameters. However, the parameters of these subsets (Tr_A and Tr_B) differ from the general population (G), hindering the translation of regression based predictive models to the general population.

10.2.1 Alternative

A conceptual alternative envisions the RCT binary data matrix as a mix of randomly distributed and deterministically related elements. Within the RCT binary data matrix, individuals are independent, and deterministic relationships occur within individuals, not across them. Forming an aggregate from components

by structural assembly, or the physical relatedness of atoms creating a molecule through random encounters can be examples of deterministic relationships. The clusters of deterministically related variables can be identical in some individuals and differ in others. This metaphorical "soup" consists of solid components (aggregations of deterministically related elements) and dispersed, randomly distributed elements in the "broth."

In this model, expressions, for example, like $Pr(A \cap B) \leq 0.001$ may indicate the probability of chance encounters between elements or components, where the values, e.g., smaller than 0.0001 suggest deterministic relationships. This perspective underscores the "physical" nature of relationships within the RCT binary data matrix, emphasizing the "actual world of experiment" as opposed to the "purely mathematical development of theory." xlii

10.2.2 Case 9

In this context, let's Peter (In_{pt}) be the RCT subject from the trial sample Tr_A . Among the variables describing Peter, there is a cluster of variables $(tx \cap Y), A, B, G, h, I$ deterministically related to each other, which is confirmed using yet-to-be-developed criteria.

Another individual, Paul (In_{pl}), from the training sample (Tr_B) is observed to have the cluster of variables A, B, G, h, I . As previously demonstrated, this cluster is a subset of the deterministically related set of variables $(tx \cap Y), A, B, G, h, I$, i.e., the cluster A, B, G, h, I is a marker for $(tx \cap Y)$. Consequently, it can be inferred that Paul also possesses the property Sp_+ .

Generally, as shown above, if the cluster of variables is convincingly identified as the constituent of the aggregation in one of the samples of the general population, it holds the status of aggregation in other samples of the general population regardless of the parameters of the variables comprising the aggregation in the samples. Upon having established that the probability of the cluster $(tx \cap Y), A, B, G, h, I$ is below the criterion C , the identification of the result of treatment in patient possessing the cluster of deterministically related variables does not depend on the parameters of these variables in the samples (Tr_A) and (Tr_B).

Metaphorically, a specific solid component in a soup has the same property in each cap, as well as in the pot from which the soup was poured into the caps. This property of the solid component remains consistent, regardless of the thickness or liquidness of each portion. We recognize a pea in any portion of the soup by its specific combination of form, color, taste, viscosity, etc., rather than relying on an exhaustive list of chemical compounds, whose concentrations are provided on a label as required by health authorities. It can be helpful and necessary in an appropriate context, but it is not that we usually use to identify the pea.

The prediction that Paul has the property Sp_+ has been made based only on the discovery that he has the cluster of the deterministically related variables A, B, G, h, I . Also, it is unaffected by the parameters of these variables in the general population (G). Therefore, if then the cluster A, B, G, h, I is observed in an individual Mary (In_M), from the general population, it implies that Mary also has the property Sp_+ .

With necessary reservations and disclaimers required in clinical practice, we can inform Mary (In_l) that the treatment Tx (which is complex, painful, bothersome, expensive, and carries risks for serious adverse reactions), may not be needed to her because she is expected to recover spontaneously.

10.3 Principles of Predicting Individual Response to Treatment

Just a reminder that an *individual's response to treatment* is formed by a diverse array of physical characteristics, stemming from both intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Our report^{xliii} offers a comprehensive exploration of this intricate complexity. Within the RCT database, these factors manifest as covariates. Conceptually, these attributes can be classified as sensitivity to treatment (St) and/or capacity for spontaneous

recovery (Sp), with the understanding that they are not mutually exclusive. These properties, St and/or Sp , serve as pivotal elements within the treatment context. A positive outcome hinges on an individual either exhibiting sensitivity to treatment (St_+) or possessing the capacity for spontaneous recovery (Sp_+). In contrast, a negative outcome arises in the absence of these properties.

Predicting the *individual response to treatment* is thought here as complement to predicting the *treatment effect* in the frame of the predictive HTE analysis. The indices of the predicted *treatment effect* serve as a characterization of the population, group, or subgroup. As shown above, the claimed identification and predicting the *individual treatment effect*^{div} in fact entails predicting the individual outcome, rather than the *treatment effect*.

The population is modeled as a mix of deterministically related and randomly distributed variables. Individuals are independent, and the set of variables describing the individual may include subsets of deterministically related (aggregated) elements, as well as randomly distributed variables. Some of the aggregations may include the treatment outcome complex, i.e., combination of treatment and outcome.

The training population (RCT dataset in our demonstration case) is a nonrandom (selected based on inclusion-exclusion criteria) sample of the general population. The parameters of the distribution of the variables may be (and are) different in the general population and its samples, but the structure of the aggregation identified within, e.g., the RCT population is identical to the relevant aggregation within the general population and its samples.

For instance, the aggregation $Ag_a \supset (tx, Y), Cl_i$ belongs to the individual, who was not treated with the treatment Tx , who has recovered (Y), and who has the cluster of the variables deterministically related to each other and to the variables tx and Y . As far as the member of the general population has a cluster of variables identical to the cluster Cl_i of the aggregation Ag_a , it can be inferred that if he/she will not be treated with Tx , he/she still will recover.

Similarly, the clusters of variables deterministically related to other combinations of treatment and outcome served for other predictions systematized in Table 3.

10.4 Content of Predictions of Individual Response to Treatment

In the best-case scenario, the prediction of the *individual response to treatment* encompasses a set of clinically significant characteristics including the presence/absence of the properties of capacity for spontaneous recovery (Sp_+) and/or sensitivity to the treatment (St_+). Having data on these determinants of the individual response to the treatment, within the treatment context, the inferences can be made about the outcome under condition of Tx , or tx , as well as the inference about the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the treatment in this individual, which as shown above, is a different issue. Separately, it can be inferred whether this treatment should or should not be provided to this individual.

For instance, the individual has the property making him/her sensitive to treatment Tx , but there is no need to prescribe it to this patient as he/she is expected to recover spontaneously.

For other patients, a more limited set of predictions is possible. Finally, for the individuals whose sets of covariates does not include the clusters identical to the predictive ones, the predictions can only be made in the frame of the predicting the *treatment effect* as the proportion of the outcome of interest, Average Treatment Effect (ATE), or odds ratio, etc., characterizing the relevant population, group, or subgroup rather than an individual. The modern approaches, as mentioned above, can predict the individual outcome, but cannot characterize the individual treatment effect.

Certainly, the clinical judgement may involve the factors and considerations not accounted for in the formal predictions.

10.5 Process of Predictions of the Individual Response to Treatment

I Combination of treatment & outcome in predictive cluster		II		III		IV Response to treatment	V Recommendation on treatment
		a	b	c	d		
		Properties Sp & St		Outcome predicted in those exposed to			
		Definitely	Possibly	Tx	tx		
Tx, Y	Cluster 1 Cluster 2 Cluster ...	$St_+ \cup Sp_+$	$St_+ \cap Sp_+$	Y	$Y? y?$	Recovery can be either treatment-induced or spontaneous	Tx is indicated
Tx, y	Cluster a+1 Cluster a+2 Cluster a+...	$St_- \cap Sp_-$	N/A	y	y	Recovery in response to Tx is not expected.	Explore effective alternative to Tx
tx, Y	Cluster b+1 Cluster b+2 Cluster b+...	Sp_+	St_+	Y	Y	Spontaneous recovery is expected.	No need for Tx
tx, y	Cluster c+1 Cluster c+2 Cluster c+...	Sp_-	$St_+ \cup St_-$	$Y?$	y	Sensitivity to Tx is not ruled out	If there is no reliable alternative, it makes sense to try Tx
Random		N/A	N/A	$Y? y?$	$Y? y?$	No information on individual response to Tx .	To assess group risk/benefit ratio

Table 3. Identification and prediction of individual response to treatment.

Predictions on the individual's *response to treatment* are not uniform for all cases and depend on available information. Table 3 illustrates the content, variants, and the process of identifying and predicting individual responses to treatment.

10.5.1 Identifying aggregations

The process begins with identifying aggregations, each of which includes the "treatment-outcome complex" ($Tx, Y; Tx, y; tx, Y$; or tx, y) among the individuals comprising the training set (Tr). Our training set (Tr) is the RCT data matrix.

Let an individual In_j be described as, e.g., $In_j \supset (tx, Y), C \supset (Cl_i, \dots)$; which means that he/she was not treated with Tx , had the outcome Y and a set of covariates C including the clusters Cl_i, \dots defining the aggregations Ag_i , and comprised of the covariates deterministically related covariates.

Table 3 records the clusters Cl_i, \dots, Cl_{i+k} deterministically related to the combination of treatment tx and outcome Y .

10.5.2 Reformulating

The "treatment-outcome complex" in the individual may relate to more than one aggregation, enabling reformulation of the list of aggregations including the "treatment-outcome complex" as a list of predictive clusters Cl_i (markers), each linked to one "treatment-outcome complex." (Table 3, Column I).

10.5.3 Cross-walking

Subsequently, the set of covariates of the individual from the general population subjected to predictions (e.g., In_M) should be compared (cross-walked) against the list of the predictive clusters (markers).

10.5.4 Identifying outcome

For instance, In_M (who is a member of general population) is found having the cluster of the variables identical to the predictive Cluster $b2$. It can be predicted that that In_M will have the outcome Y if not treated with Tx , because the predictive cluster Cl_{b2} is deterministically related to the combination tx, Y .

10.5.5 Identifying determinants of response to treatment

Having identified the predictive cluster (and, therefore, the respective "treatment-outcome complex") in the subject enables the inference about the presence or absence of determinants (Sp_+ , St_+ , or both) of the *response to treatment* (Column IIa,b). Note that these inferences can be either definite (Column IIa) or indicate a possibility (Column IIb) of the presence or absence of these property(ies) in this individual. For example, the individual In_M *definitely* has the property Sp_+ ; also it is *possible* (but not necessarily) that she has the property St_+ .

10.5.6 Predicting response of the individual to treatment

Since the individual In_M has the property Sp_+ , she will recover regardless of having received the treatment Tx , or not, i.e. she will have the outcome Y (Column IIIc). By that reason, the presence or absence of the property St_+ in this case, in the individual In_M , does not make a difference. In other cases, e.g., where the property Sp_+ is lacking, the presence or absence of this property will have a decisive impact on the treatment strategy.

10.5.7 Recommendation on treatment

In the case of In_M , the recommendation should be that this patient does not need the treatment Tx since she is expected to recover spontaneously.

10.6 Variability of predictions

In other cases, the recommendations may be or not be that straightforward. For instance, the combination Tx, y allows for only one possible interpretation of the relationships between the treatment and outcome: the individual with this combination has neither Sp_+ , nor St_+ . In other cases, the observed combination of the treatment and outcome (Tx, Y ; tx, Y ; or tx, y) is the realization of one, or two, or more possible combinations of the properties Sp_+ , St_+ , Sp_- , and St_- . The recommendations on treatment (column V) account for this variability.

For instance, an individual In_N from the general population has a cluster of covariates Cl_{c1} corresponding to the treatment-outcome complex $Tx Y$. For In_N it means that he/she can three possible combinations of the

properties: $(Sp_+$ and $St_+)$, $(Sp_+$ and $St_-)$, or $(Sp_-$ and $St_+)$. It is possible that this individual will recover spontaneously, but since the variant $(Sp_-$ and $St_+)$ cannot be ruled out, also there is risk for a negative outcome. Therefore, a positive outcome can be predicted only under condition of prescribing the treatment Tx to this individual.

The recommendations, which derive from analysis of the structure of the determinants of the treatment response, also should account for a broader clinical context.

For instance, for individual In_0 (general population), who has, for example, a cluster Cl_{d1} related to the treatment-outcome complex $tx y$. Apparently, this combination of treatment and outcome does not contain any direct information on the potential effect of the treatment Tx . However, it cannot be ruled out that he/she may have the property St_+ , which means that if there is no more reliable treatment opportunity available, it makes sense to prescribe the treatment Tx .

If, for instance, for individual In_0 (general population) it is predicted that treatment Tx will not be effective ($Tx y$). In this case, prescribing the treatment Tx is not indicated. Resources can be more efficiently allocated to explore alternative possibilities for treatments. Also, unnecessary risk of severe adverse effects related to treatment Tx can be avoided.

Yet, in all the cases, clinicians may have serious considerations beyond this logic in favor of prescribing or not prescribing the treatment.

10.7 Absence of predictive cluster

Predicting *the individual response to treatment* is complementary to predicting the individual outcome in the context of studying the *treatment effect*. Having predicted *the individual response to treatment* in the individuals having the identified markers does not preclude the assessment of the population-oriented aspect of the *treatment effect* utilizing traditional metrics. Also, if the individual from the general population, e.g., In_R , does not have the cluster of covariates identical to any predictive one, there remains the opportunity of predicting his/her outcome using the traditional means of the predictive HTE analysis.

10.8 Clinical relevance

The data on the efficacy obtained from RCT are the major driver of the physician's treatment decisions regarding the medicine examined in the trial. They are provided to physicians as the indices characterizing risk (change in risk, odds ratio, etc.) for a whole population (group, or subgroup). In clinical practice, the distinction between the group risk and individual risk is vaguely designated.^{xlv} Typically, each individual from this population (group, or subgroup) is meant as a carrier of the group risk factor, i.e., the group risk is thought as his/her virtual individual property. However, the individual risk can never be verified: in the individual with an observed positive outcome the individual risk was overestimated, and for the individual a negative outcome it was underestimated^{xlvi}

While treating an individual patient, the physician uses the indices of the predicted *group treatment effect* as a general indication of direction, but in the individual treatment decision he/she appeals to his/her experience and intuition. In fact, the role of intuition and experience is even more important since the accuracy of the predictions achieved within the training population (e.g., RCT), cannot be transferred to the general population. On the other hand, the physician experiences some social pressure to prescribe the treatment, even marginal efficacy of which is shown in RCT, rather than to appeal to his/her understanding of heterogeneity of *treatment effect/response to treatment*, and his/her experience and intuition.

In this regard, the presented *response to treatment* approach should be the instrument to support individualized treatment decisions.

11 Conclusion: Considerations, Limitations, and Perspectives

Our study has demonstrated the potential for integrating statistical and logical approaches to enable causal inferences (in a broad sense) and predict the *individual response to treatment*. The proposed *response-to-treatment* approach is a tool for analyzing heterogeneous populations, which can be generally described as a mix of deterministically related and randomly scattered elements.

Advancements in individualization necessitate the utilization of contemporary statistical and computational approaches, including machine learning, deep learning, and artificial intelligence (AI). The efficacy of these approaches hinges on the symbiotic relationship between the investigator and these technologies, contingent upon the formulation of pertinent questions and the provision of comprehensive conceptual guidance. In this regard, our exploratory approach, which offers a non-traditional perspective, has the potential to yield substantial new findings.

Contrary to the statistical approach to studying the *treatment effect*, assumptions underlying the *response-to-treatment* approach are rooted in traditional qualitative clinical thinking. When applied to quantitative data, this approach seeks to merge the flexibility and exploratory nature of qualitative clinical methods with the benefits of quantification, measurement, and computation. However, this integration necessitates a trade-off: the flexibility inherent in qualitative approaches must be constrained by the demands of quantitative methods. Combining logical and statistical approaches offers a natural pathway for investigating this area. More specifically, it represents a foundational step that contrasts sharply with the trajectory of the rapidly advancing field of contemporary artificial intelligence (AI). Paradoxically, we contend that these approaches will inevitably be integrated through the interaction between artificial and human intelligence, influencing how both are applied and understood.

In the ongoing dispute regarding the possibility of drawing causal inferences from single cases, by exploring a classic example, we have supported the position that inferences from individual cases regarding the effect of treatment are possible within the statistical context, provided the relevant study design and the appropriately examined correspondence between the treatment's capacity to produce the effect and the individual's capacity to respond.

Furthermore, we demonstrated that inferences regarding the effect of treatment in an individual case are possible in a purely logical context provided switching focus from potential outcomes to analysis of the factual (observed) outcomes. The integration of logical and statistical analysis enables mapping the covariates or clusters of covariates deterministically related to the combination of treatment and outcome. In fact, this is the identification of the *markers* for the *individual response to treatment* within the trial population, and it enables predicting *the* response in individual cases beyond the trial boundaries, although it is feasible not for all cases.

Unlike the indices of the *treatment effect*, which characterize the entire population, group, or subgroup, not the individual member, predicting the *individual response to treatment* varies among subjects depending on available information. In the best-case scenario, an *individual's response to treatment* can be predicted for some individuals from the general population using a comprehensive set of clinically significant characteristics. In other cases, predictions may be based on separate elements of this set or may be unattainable for individuals whose covariates do not match predictive clusters. For these individuals, predictions may be limited to group-level metrics such as proportions, average treatment effects, or odds ratios, etc., in the frame of the traditional *treatment effect* approach.

This limitation could potentially be mitigated by expanding the set of covariates and/or increasing the size of the training sample/population. Therefore, identification and prediction of the *individual response to treatment* complements the *treatment effect* approach specifically in areas, in which the latter has limitations, particularly in predicting the effect of treatment for individuals from the general population.

In this paper, our analyses stemmed from RCT data. With necessary adjustments, this approach can be applied to the exploration and analysis of treatment using observational, messy, and incomplete data, as well as the analysis of single cases and small groups. In this context, the status of aggregation can be confirmed or rejected using valid and reliable epidemiological data on relevant characteristics of the studied population.

Currently, only basic statistical procedures can be advised in the context of *response-to-treatment* analysis. The binary model used in this investigation was convenient to present the idea. Besides, it was adequate for the binary categories of treatment and binary outcome (e.g., “recovery vs. death. Generalization to continuous outcomes would be a natural next step and follows the same principles. The development of the criterion discerning the aggregation of the deterministically related elements from the randomly gathered elements should be another step.

More advanced quantitative methods specifically focusing on the analysis of the *response to treatment* are yet to be explored or developed. Further development will enable the application of this approach to more structurally complex aggregation of the factors determining the individual *response to treatment*.

11.1 Potential Applications

The described approach has potential applications in:

- *Clinical medicine*: as a tool facilitating individualized treatment decisions.
- *Clinical and epidemiological research*: secondary analysis of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and observational studies on heterogeneity of the *response to treatment*, exploring individual and small group responses to treatment as a complement to heterogeneous treatment effect (HTE) predictive analysis, with the possibility of extending predictions beyond the boundaries of RCT or observational study datasets.
- *Genetics*: genetics of rare disorders; family genetics, pharmacogenetics.
- *Drug Development*: secondary analysis of RCT data, identification sub-populations having a positive response (not just a positive outcome) to the drug dimmed ineffective, and the sub-populations having a negative response to the drug qualified effective based on the assessment of the *treatment effect* in RCTs.
- *Drug safety and pharmacovigilance*: RCT monitoring, as well as post-marketing signal detection and evaluation.
- *Beyond medicine and drug development context*: Further impact may be sought in a broad class of areas and populations characterized by heterogeneity of response to treatment, where understanding and addressing the members of the population in an individualized manner can render better results for a smaller expenditure.

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